

Scientific Papers of the
National Research Council Canada
Five Biotechnology Research Institutes

A Bibliometric Analysis

Éric Archambault
Yannick Melançon

November 2000

Observatoire des sciences et des technologies
3465, rue Durocher Montréal (Québec) H2X 2C6
Téléphone : (514) 499-4074 Télécopieur : (514) 499-4065
www.ost.qc.ca

Contents

Summary.....	i
1. Introduction	1
2. NRC Biotechnology Institutes and their Comparable Institutes	2
3. Canadian Scientific Research Papers	3
4. Number of Papers	5
5. Distribution by Field.....	6
6. Appliedness	10
7. Impact Factor	11
8. Scientific Collaboration.....	13
9. Conclusion	17
Definitions	19

Tables

Table 1	Papers of NRC Biotechnology Institutes by Field, 1992-1997	6
Table 2	Percentage of Papers by Discipline of the NRC Biotechnology Program and Comparable Institutes, 1992-1997	7
Table 3	Papers in Biomedical Research, 1992-1997.....	8
Table 4	Papers in Biology, 1992-1997	8
Table 5	Index of Specialization* by Field, 1992-1997	9
Table 6	Index of Specialization* of NRC Biotechnology Institutes and Comparables by Field, 1992-1997	9
Table 7	Degree of Appliedness of Papers by the NRC, the Federal Government, Canada and the G7 Countries, 1992-1997	10
Table 8	Degree of Appliedness of Papers by the NRC Biotechnology Institutes, 1992-1997.....	10
Table 9	Degree of Appliedness of Papers by the NRC Biotechnology Institutes and Comparable Institutes, 1992-1997	11
Table 10	Average Relative Impact Factor* by Year, 1992-1997.....	12
Table 11	Average Relative Impact Factor* of NRC Biotechnology Institutes and Comparable Institutes by Field, 1992-1997	12
Table 12	Provincial Collaborations of NRC Biotechnology Institutes, 1992-1997.....	14
Table 13	Number of national collaboration by sector, 1992-1997.....	15
Table 14	Productivity ratios for NRC biotechnology institutes, 1992-1997.....	17

Figures

Figure 1	Number of Canadian Scientific Papers, 1992-1997	3
Figure 2	Percentage of Canadian Papers Relative to G7 Countries, 1992-1997.....	3
Figure 3	Number of Scientific Papers from the Federal Government and from NRC, 1992-1997.....	4
Figure 4	Number of Papers from NRC Biotechnology Institutes, 1992-1997	5
Figure 5	Average Number of Papers from NRC Biotechnology Institutes and from Comparable Institutes, 1992-1997	6
Figure 6	Papers in Biomedical Research from NRC Biotechnology Program.....	7
Figure 7	Collaborations of the NRC Biotechnology Program at the National and International Levels, 1992-1997	13
Figure 8	Distribution of National Collaboration of NRC Biotechnology Program, 1992-1997.....	14
Figure 9	Average Number of International Collaborations for NRC Biotechnology Institutes and for Comparable Institutes, 1992-1997	16

Summary

- Between 1992 and 1997, NRC biotechnology institutes published 1 614 papers which account for 1,1% of the Canadian papers (p.5).
- Relative to NRC as a whole, the share of papers from the biotechnology program has been stable over the 1992-1997 period with 32% of the NRC papers (p.5).
- The majority of papers from NRC's biotechnology program pertained to the health sector (biomedical research and clinical medicine - 66% of the papers), followed by biology (15%) and chemistry (14%) (pp.6-7).
- Within the field of biomedical research, the largest number of papers was in the sub-fields of biochemistry and molecular biology. The NRC biotechnology program account for 72% of the papers by the Canadian federal government and 5,3% of the Canadian papers in this sub-field. (pp.7-8).
- In biology, the largest number of papers was in the botany sub-field. The NRC biotechnology program accounted for 12% of the papers by the Canadian federal government and 4% of the Canadian papers in this sub-field (p.8).
- The papers of NRC biotechnology institutes are close to the fundamental side of the appliedness scale (p.10).
- The average paper produced by NRC biotechnology program from 1992-1997 had a greater impact than the average one published by the G7 countries (p.11). The NRC biotechnology institutes all had a greater relative impact factor than their comparable research institutes (p.12).
- The share of papers written in international collaboration rose from 22% to 33%, which is similar to the trend observed for Canada as a whole. National collaborations were stable at around 42% of the total number of papers (p.13).
- Canadian universities, particularly those closely located to NRC laboratories, comprised the largest number of NRC's national collaborations (pp.14-15).
- The biotechnology program as a whole produces papers of a similar quality to the rest of NRC. Globally, the five institutes showed a good performance relative to their comparables and relative to G7 (pp.17-18).

1. Introduction

This report provides a quantitative overview of National Research Council of Canada's (NRC) production of scientific knowledge from 1992 to 1997 in the field of biotechnology. It focuses on one important output of the NRC scientific research effort in biotechnology, the publication of scientific research (papers). This is not the only indicator available but it is one of the more widely used to analyse the scientific output of research laboratories.

This analysis uses three types of documents that are undisputedly accepted as original contributions to scientific knowledge: Articles, Notes and Reviews¹. The report refers to these three types of documents as "papers". The report uses the metric system and decimal notation.

The study draws on the Observatoire des sciences et des technologies' (OST) bibliometric database which contains publications from some 3 750 scientific journals indexed by the Institute for Scientific Information (ISI)². These are considered to be the most important peer-reviewed journals. They reflect significant scientific achievements and are the most widely cited (80% of the world's citations).

OST has standardised the way addresses appear in every paper written by Canadian researchers between 1980 and 1997. This procedure involved a standardisation of the names of institutions and cities in order to compute precise statistics. The database on scientific publications includes approximately 2 800 different Canadian institutional addresses. In addition, each institution received a code that corresponds to a sector of activity: university, college, hospital, government (federal or provincial), industry, and other. Finally, each journal was assigned a field (biology, biomedical research, chemistry, clinical medicine, earth and space science, engineering and technology, mathematics, physics), and a sub-field (100 specialities), a degree of appliedness and a yearly impact factor. The field, sub-field and degree of appliedness for each journal were obtained from the classification produced by CHI Research Inc. for the National Science Foundation of the United States, and the impact factor from the Journal Citation Reports produced by the Institute for Scientific Information.

Section 2 describes the five NRC biotechnology institutes and their comparable institutes. Section 3 presents data on Canadian scientific papers in order to provide a context to analyse the output from the NRC biotechnology programme. This section also presents data on the papers of the federal government together with those of NRC.

Section 4 presents data on the number of papers by each of the NRC biotechnology institutes while Section 5 analyses their distribution by field and by sub-field. Section 6 analyses the degree of appliedness of the papers while Section 7 analyses their impact factors. Finally, Section 8 analyses the pattern of scientific collaboration by the NRC biotechnology institutes.

¹ Out of 23 used in the SCI including items Editorial, Book-review, Biographical Item, Music-Score-Review.

² A list of the journals can be found at <http://www.isinet.com/isi/products/citation/sci> (Institute for Scientific Information, Philadelphia, PA).

2. NRC Biotechnology Institutes and their Comparable Institutes

The focus of this study is on the NRC's five biotechnology research institutes:

- Biotechnology Research Institute (BRI)
- Institute for Biodiagnostics (IBD)
- Institute of Biological Science (IBS)
- Institute for Marine Biology (IMB)
- Plant Biotechnology Institute (PBI)

Collectively, these research institutes form the NRC biotechnology program. Each institute has been compared to two government-funded research institutes that performed similar research activities. These comparable institutes have been identified in collaboration with the five NRC biotechnology institutes.

Located in Montreal, BRI performs research projects in molecular biology and biochemical engineering. It concentrates its resources on collaborative projects with Canadian industry, particularly companies working in the pharmaceutical and resource sectors. BRI's two comparables are the Gesellschaft für Biotechnologische Forschung (GBF) and the Institut für Biotechnologie (IBT), both located in Germany.

Located in Winnipeg, IBD carries out research in non-invasive approaches to diagnosing diseases and monitoring treatment, collaborating with medical device and pharmaceutical industries. IBD's two comparables are the Institut für Biomedizinische Technik (IBMT) located in Germany and the Stiftelsen for industriell og teknologisk forskning (SINTEF) located in Norway.

Located in Ottawa, IBS does research in neurobiology and immunochemistry of importance to the health and pharmaceutical sectors. IBS's two comparable institutes are the Nencki Institute of Experimental Biology (Nencki) located in Poland and the Forschungszentrum Borstel Zentrum für Medizin und Biowissenschaften (ZMB) located in Germany.

Located in Halifax, IMB carries out research in aquaculture (fish health, nutrition, species diversification and seafood safety) and genomics (DNA sequencing, proteomics, bioinformatics). The two institutes that are comparable to IMB are the Australian Institute of Marine Science (AIMS) and the Pacific Region Division (Pacific) of Fisheries and Oceans Canada.

Located in Saskatoon, PBI's mission is to perform, assist and promote strategic research in plant biotechnology by re-programming gene expression machinery to produce desirable characteristics in crop plants to suit specific needs. PBI's two comparable institutes are the Eastern Cereal and Oilseed Research Centre (ECORC) of Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada and the Plant Industry Division of the Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO) in Australia.

3. Canadian Scientific Research Papers

This section provides a background for the interpretation of the trends pertaining to NRC's biotechnology program. It presents of the Canadian federal government, excluding NRC contributions. The aim is to identify the trends that are specific to each entities. Likewise, NRC biotechnology program are separate from other NRC contributions.

The number of Canadian scientific papers has been relatively stable in the 1990s with about 25 000 papers published yearly (Figure 1). However, with increased growth in papers between 1990 and 1997 by the G7 countries (from 355 000 to 393 000 papers), the stabilization of Canadian production has created a slight decline in its relative position on the G7 scene, from 7% in 1992 to 6,4% in 1997 (Figure 2).

Figure 1 Number of Canadian Scientific Papers, 1992-1997

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

Figure 2 Percentage of Canadian Papers Relative to G7 Countries, 1992-1997

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

The number of papers from the Canadian federal government (excluding NRC) has been rather stable between 1992 and 1997, with a small drop from 2 966 to 2 850 papers (Figure

3). Relative to Canadian papers, the share of the federal government has fallen slightly over the period, that is, from 12% to 11,4%.

During that period, the number of scientific papers from NRC laboratories (excluding the biotechnology program) has dropped 19% - from 621 to 503 (Figure 3). The share of NRC papers relative to federal government papers remained around 20% between 1992 and 1997.

Figure 3 Number of Scientific Papers from the Federal Government and from NRC, 1992-1997

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

N.B. Federal government papers do not include NRC papers and NRC papers do not include those from the NRC biotechnology program.

4. Number of Papers

Between 1992 and 1997, NRC's biotechnology program published 1614 papers which account for 1,1% of the Canadian papers. Relative to NRC as a whole, the share of papers from the biotechnology program has been stable over the 1992-1997 period with 32% of NRC papers. However, this picture differs between institutes.

BRI produced the largest number of papers between 1992 and 1997 followed by IBS (Figure 4). IBD had the fastest growth during the period³. IMB and PBI had small fluctuations in the number of scientific papers with a small downward trend.

Figure 4 Number of Papers from NRC Biotechnology Institutes, 1992-1997

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

The number of scientific papers published by the five NRC biotechnology institutes has followed a similar movement to that of Canadian papers, with a small drop of 8% over the period. The average number of papers from NRC biotechnology institutes has gone down slightly over that period (58 to 53 annually). By contrast, over the same period the comparable research institutes slightly increased their average number of papers, that is, from 62 to 68 annually (Figure 5)⁴.

³ IBD was established in Winnipeg, Manitoba in March 1992. A number of the researchers at IBD were relocated from two of NRC's Ottawa Institutes: IBS and Steacie Institute for Molecular Sciences. (<http://www.ibd.nrc.ca/ibd/more-ibd.html>). In this context, it is not surprising to observe that IBS's publication count has gone down proportionately to the rise of IBD's.

⁴ Since the data on the number of employees per year are not available for these research institutes, it is not possible to know whether this growth is due to increased productivity or to increased staff.

Figure 5 Average Number of Papers from NRC Biotechnology Institutes and from Comparable Institutes, 1992-1997

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

5. Distribution by Field

The NRC biotechnology institutes have published the majority of their papers (53%) in the field of biomedical research (Table 1). The papers published by the five NRC institutes account for 38% of the papers of the federal government in biomedical research. Three other fields have received a sizeable share of NRC's papers: biology (15%), chemistry (14%) and clinical medicine (13%).

The NRC papers in biomedical research are principally produced by two institutes: BRI and IBS. PBI and IMB published a majority of papers in the field of biology whereas IBD is more present in the field of clinical medicine.

Table 1 Papers of NRC Biotechnology Institutes by Field, 1992-1997

	BRI	IBD	IBS	IMB	PBI	TOTAL	N	NRC* (N)	Fed** (N)	Canada (N)	G7 (N)
Biology	16	1	7	82	139	245	244	83	6 166	19 295	167 498
Biomedical Research	413	50	302	54	71	890	862	118	1 388	26 067	401 950
Chemistry	50	36	45	80	17	228	225	625	1 393	14 143	255 851
Clinical Medicine	27	74	97	12	1	211	206	60	1 310	46 123	766 605
Earth And Space	14	2	1	1		18	18	643	3 949	13 003	123 339
Engineering & Techn	9	1	1	7		18	18	512	1 485	13 798	181 455
Mathematics						0	0	3	44	3 423	42 651
Physics	13	10	8	3		34	34	1 409	2 073	15 800	320 249
Unknown	5		2			7	7	1	40	484	12 159
TOTAL	547	174	463	239	228	1 651	1 614	3 454	17 848	152 136	2 271 757

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

* Excluding the 5 NRC biotechnology centres

** Excluding NRC

The majority of papers from NRC's biotechnology program pertained to the health sector (biomedical research and clinical medicine - 66% of the papers), followed by biology (15%) and chemistry (14%). This is also true for the comparable research institutes

although they published a greater number of papers in the field of biology and fewer in biomedical research (Table 2)

Table 2 Percentage of Papers by Discipline of the NRC Biotechnology Program and Comparable Institutes, 1992-1997

	NRC Biotech	Comparables
Biology	14,8%	37,6%
Biomedical Research	53,9%	36,1%
Chemistry	13,8%	5,9%
Clinical Medicine	12,8%	14,3%
Earth and Space	1,1%	3,9%
Engineering & Technology	1,1%	1,2%
Mathematics	0,0%	0,0%
Physics	0,3%	0,1%
Unknown	0,1%	0,1%
TOTAL	100%	100%

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

Although the majority of papers from NRC biotechnology program were published in journals in the field of biomedical research, the number of papers in this field has fallen from 163 in 1994 to 121 in 1997 - that is, from 58% down to 46% of the biotechnology program papers (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Papers in Biomedical Research from NRC Biotechnology Program

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

As expected, within the field of biomedical research, the largest number of papers is in the sub-fields of biochemistry and molecular biology (Table 3) where NRC's biotechnology program accounts for 72% of the papers by the Canadian government.

Table 3 Papers in Biomedical Research, 1992-1997

	BRI	IBD	IBS	IMB	PBI	TOTAL	N	NRC* (N)	Fed** (N)	Canada (N)	G7 (N)
Biomedical Research	413	50	302	54	71	890	862	118	1 388	26 067	401 950
Anatomy & Morphology						0			1	243	3 321
Biochem & Molec Biol	220	38	205	27	32	522	505	48	207	9 470	152 946
Biomedical Enginrng	60	1	7		1	69	69	2	52	1 069	13 805
Biophysics	1	5	7			13	12	1	5	413	5 150
Cell Biol Cyt & Hist	13	2	21	1	13	50	49	3	33	1 416	26 886
Embryology						0		1	6	242	4 264
Genetics & Heredity	25		5	10	17	57	56	4	219	3 407	42 579
Genrl Biomedical Res	36	1	5	6	1	49	46	30	121	2 176	48 425
Microbiology	39		43	8	7	97	93	3	353	2 288	30 994
Microscopy						0		16	26	202	3 166
Misc Biomedical Res		1	4			5	5	3	83	493	8 015
Nutrition & Dietet	1		1			2	2	2	76	699	10 307
Parasitology	2			2		4	4		54	436	7 133
Physiology	2	2	2			6	5	5	61	2 673	28 827
Virology	14		2			16	16		91	840	16 132

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

* Excluding the 5 NRC biotechnology centres

** Excluding NRC

In biology, the largest number of papers was in the botany specialty (Table 4). This can be seen for both PBI as well as IMB, the latter being highly active in marine biology and hydrobiology sub-fields. NRC's biotechnology program accounted for 12% of federal government papers in botany. In the field of chemistry, the greatest number of papers was published in analytical chemistry whereas in the field of clinical medicine the greatest number of papers were published in the neurology and neurosurgery sub-fields.

Table 4 Papers in Biology, 1992-1997

	BRI	IBD	IBS	IMB	PBI	TOTAL	N	NRC* (N)	Fed** (N)	Canada (N)	G7 (N)
Biology	16	1	7	82	139	245	244	83	6 166	19 295	167 498
Agricult & Food Sci	9		1	2	15	27	27	8	2 134	4 637	37 512
Botany	1		2	42	120	165	164	6	1 205	4 514	47 983
Dairy & Animal Sci						0			552	1 527	11 643
Ecology						0		3	220	1 354	14 391
Entomology	6		1		4	11	11	1	522	1 323	13 077
General Biology			1			1	1	9	62	519	4 000
General Zoology		1				1	1	8	166	1 298	7 492
Marine Bio & Hydrobi				38		38	38	37	1 158	3 110	21 017
Miscellaneous Biol			2			2	2		16	256	3 734
Miscellaneous Zool						0		11	131	757	6 649

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

* Excluding the 5 NRC biotechnology centres

** Excluding NRC

Table 5 presents the index of specialization for the five NRC biotechnology institutes together with that of NRC excluding these five institutes, of the federal government excluding NRC and of Canada. The index shows how specialized (i.e. active) an institution is in a particular field in comparison with a given unit of reference. In this case, the reference is the whole distribution of papers of the G7 countries. An index value above 1 means that an institute is considered to be specialized in a field relative to the distribution of papers in the G7 countries (see Annex). Table 5 shows that Canada is specialized in the fields of biology (1,7) as well as earth and space (1,6) and that this is even more so for the

Canadian federal government (4,7 and 4,1). Setting aside the biotechnology institutes, NRC specializes in the fields of earth and space as well as physics.

Consistent with its quantity of papers, the NRC biotechnology program specializes in biomedical research (3,0). The second most prominent field of specialization is biology (2,1). When compared to the distribution of papers of the G7 countries, PBI is the most specialized centre with an index of 8,3 in biology. IMB is also specialized in biology, although chemistry also plays an important role (respectively 4,7 and 3,0). BRI and IBS are specialized in biomedical research, which is consistent with the large number of papers by these institutes in this field. IBD is not as clearly specialized as the other institutes of the NRC biotechnology program.

Table 5 Index of Specialization* by Field, 1992-1997

	BRI	IBD	IBS	IMB	PBI	Avg.	NRC** (N)	Fed*** (N)	Canada (N)
Biology	0,4	0,1	0,2	4,7	8,3	2,1	0,3	4,7	1,7
Biomedical Research	4,3	1,6	3,7	1,3	1,8	3,0	0,2	0,4	1,0
Chemistry	0,8	1,8	0,9	3,0	0,7	1,2	1,6	0,7	0,8
Clinical Medicine	0,1	1,3	0,6	0,1	0,0	0,4	0,1	0,2	0,9
Earth And Space	0,5	0,2	0,0	0,1		0,2	3,4	4,1	1,6
Engineering & Techn	0,2	0,1	0,0	0,4		0,1	1,9	1,0	1,1
Mathematics							0,0	0,1	1,2
Physics	0,2	0,4	0,1	0,1		0,1	2,9	0,8	0,7
Unknown	1,7		0,8			0,8	0,1	0,4	0,6

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

* Relative to G7

** Excluding the 5 NRC biotechnology centres

*** Excluding NRC

Table 6 shows that comparable institutes are similar to the NRC biotechnology institutes in terms of the distribution of their papers. For instance, similarly to BRI as well as IBS, GBF and IBT as well as Nencki and ZMB are specialized in biomedical research. AIMS and Pacific are similar to PBI while CSIRO and ECORC are similar to IMB through their specialization in the field of biology. Similarly to IBMT and SINTEF, IBD is not strongly specialized in any given field with respect to scientific papers.

Table 6 Index of Specialization* of NRC Biotechnology Institutes and Comparables by Field, 1992-1997

	BRI	GBF	IBT	IBD	IBMT	SINTEF	IBS	Nencki	ZMB	IMB	AIMS	Pacific	PBI	CSIRO	ECORC
Biology	0,4	1,5	0,6	0,1		0,7	0,2	0,5	0,1	4,7	8,1	10,2	8,3	10,6	10,1
Biomedical Research	4,3	3,5	4,3	1,6	1,3	0,5	3,7	3,6	2,1	1,3	0,4	0,8	1,8	1,0	0,7
Chemistry	0,8	1,1	1,1	1,8	1,3	0,5	0,9		0,2	3,0	0,2		0,7	0,2	0,4
Clinical Medicine	0,1	0,3	0,0	1,3	1,1	2,3	0,6	0,9	1,8	0,1	0,1	0,2	0,0	0,0	0,0
Earth and Space	0,5	0,1	0,4	0,2			0,0			0,1	5,1	0,2		0,2	1,4
Engineering & Techn	0,2	0,4	0,4	0,1	1,8	0,1	0,0	0,0		0,4	0,1				
Mathematics															
Physics	0,2	0,0	0,0	0,4	0,8	0,2	0,1			0,1	0,1			0,0	0,0
Unknown	1,7	1,8	1,8				0,8					3,1			0,3

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

*Relative to G7

6. Appliedness

In this section, the papers of NRC institutes are qualified with an indicator of their degree of appliedness. This indicator ranges from very applied (d.a. = 1) to highly fundamental (d.a. = 4) and is derived from the characteristics of each journal where papers are published.

Compared to the papers from G7 countries, those from Canadian authors in general as well as from the federal government have the same degree of appliedness, leaning more towards the fundamental end of the scale (3 on a scale of 4, see Table 7). The work being done at NRC is even more fundamental (3,3).

Table 7 Degree of Appliedness of Papers by the NRC, the Federal Government, Canada and the G7 Countries, 1992-1997

	NRC*		Fed**		Canada		G7	
	D.A.	N	D.A.	N	D.A.	N	D.A.	N
1992	3,4	621	2,9	2 966	3,0	24 672	3,0	354 276
1993	3,2	581	2,9	2 931	3,0	25 056	3,0	367 004
1994	3,3	605	3,0	3 076	3,0	25 797	3,0	380 327
1995	3,3	601	2,9	3 073	3,0	25 638	3,0	384 177
1996	3,3	541	3,0	2 920	3,0	25 666	3,0	388 175
1997	3,3	499	3,0	2 805	3,0	24 686	3,0	384 201
TOTAL (N=1607)	3,3	3 448	3,0	17 771	3,0	151 515	3,0	2 258 160

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

* Excluding the 5 NRC biotechnology centres

** Excluding NRC

The papers of NRC biotechnology institutes are very close to the fundamental end of the scale (3,7 on average, Table 8). Of these institutes, IBD publishes the most applied work (3,3 on average) with a noticeable tendency towards more applied papers over time. IBS and PBI publish the more fundamental work (with 3,8) but BRI and IMB are trailing very closely (3,7 and 3,6 respectively).

Table 8 Degree of Appliedness of Papers by the NRC Biotechnology Institutes, 1992-1997

	BRI		IBD		IBS		IMB		PBI		TOTAL	
	D.A.	N										
1992	3,7	93	3,5	11	3,8	100	3,6	45	3,8	43	3,7	292
1993	3,8	86	3,4	26	3,9	86	3,5	38	3,8	41	3,7	277
1994	3,8	98	3,7	31	3,9	82	3,7	38	3,8	39	3,8	288
1995	3,7	103	3,2	38	3,8	64	3,4	40	3,7	33	3,6	278
1996	3,8	80	3,2	27	3,8	60	3,7	47	3,7	35	3,7	249
1997	3,7	82	3,0	41	3,8	69	3,4	31	3,7	37	3,6	260
TOTAL (N=1607)	3,7	542	3,3	174	3,8	461	3,6	239	3,8	228	3,7	1 644

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

This degree of appliedness is similar to what is observed for comparable research institutes (Table 9). Only PBI is publishing work that is notably more fundamental than its two comparables. The more fundamental work is published in the field of biomedical research.

Table 9 Degree of Appliedness of Papers by the NRC Biotechnology Institutes and Comparable Institutes, 1992-1997

	BRI	GBF	IBT	IBD	IBMT	SINTEF	IBS	Nencki	ZMB	IMB	AIMS	Pacific	PBI	CSIRO	ECORC
Biology	3,1	3,7	3,6	n.s.		3,3	3,6	3,7	3,7	3,7	3,7	3,1	3,7	3,1	2,9
Biomedical Research	3,9	3,9	3,9	3,9	3,7	3,7	4,0	4,0	3,9	3,9	4,0	4,0	4,0	3,9	3,9
Chemistry	3,4	3,5	3,6	3,6	3,3	4,0	3,9		3,7	3,4	3,9		3,4	3,3	3,0
Clinical Medicine	3,5	3,2	3,3	2,7	2,5	2,9	3,3	3,8	2,7	2,8	3,1	3,5	n.s.	2,0	3,3
Earth and Space	2,1	3,0	2,7	n.s.			n.s.			n.s.	3,5	n.s.		2,9	2,9
Engineering & Techn	1,8	1,5	1,6	n.s.	2,0	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.		1,9	n.s.				
Mathematics															
Physics	3,8	4,0	n.s.	3,8	3,8	4,0	4,0			4,0	3,0			3,0	n.s.
Unknown															
TOTAL	3,7	3,7	3,8	3,3	3,0	3,1	3,8	3,9	3,2	3,6	3,6	3,3	3,8	3,2	3,0

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

n.s. = non-significant (less than three papers published in journals with known impact factors).

7. Impact Factor

The quality of NRC papers can be assessed with an indicator of their impact. The impact factor is calculated yearly for each scientific journal. It is the average number of citations received during a year for all the papers published in the journal over the course of two preceding years. This factor is then used to calculate the expected impact for every paper published in a given journal.

The impact factor is therefore, strictly speaking, a measurement of visibility, or influence, of the journals and their papers. Applied to the papers of a group of researchers, the impact factor is considered a legitimate indicator of research quality and its impact in the scientific community (see the Annex for greater details on the impact factor).

Table 10 presents average relative impact factors, which measure the quality of papers from NRC biotechnology institutes, NRC excluding the five biotechnology institutes, the Canadian Federal Government excluding NRC, as well as Canadian papers as a whole, relative to those published by G7 countries as a whole. An average relative factor lower than one denotes an average impact below the G7 average whereas a factor above 1 reveals an average impact greater than that of the average G7 country paper. Canadian papers are slightly above the G7 average (1,08) whereas the average paper from the Canadian federal government is on a par with G7 countries (0,99). NRC excluding the biotechnology program has an impact that is 17% greater than the G7 average.

The average paper produced by the NRC biotechnology program has a 15% greater impact than the average paper published by the G7 countries (Table 10). The highest relative

impact factors were found in BRI and PBI followed by IMB and IBS. IBD had a similar relative impact factor to that of an average scientific paper in the G7 countries.

Table 10 Average Relative Impact Factor* by Year, 1992-1997

	BRI	IBD	IBS	IMB	PBI	TOTAL	NRC**	Fed***	Canada
1992	1,2	0,8	1,1	1,1	1,2	1,1	1,1	1,0	1,1
1993	1,3	1,1	1,0	1,2	0,9	1,1	1,2	1,0	1,1
1994	1,2	0,9	1,1	1,2	1,3	1,1	1,2	1,0	1,1
1995	1,2	1,2	1,2	1,2	1,1	1,2	1,2	1,0	1,1
1996	1,2	0,9	0,9	1,1	1,2	1,1	1,2	1,0	1,1
1997	1,4	1,1	1,2	1,1	1,4	1,3	1,2	1,0	1,1
TOTAL (N=1568)	1,23	1,02	1,08	1,14	1,21	1,15	1,17	0,99	1,08

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

* Relative to G7

** Excluding the 5 NRC biotechnology institutes

*** Excluding NRC

The NRC biotechnology institutes all have similar or greater average relative impact factors than comparable research institutes (Table 11). IMB and PBI had a significant impact factor in the field where they specialize (biology). BRI had a greater impact factor than G7 countries in its field of specialization (biomedical research). IBS had the same impact factor as the average G7 countries paper in its field of specialization (also biomedical research). IBD, which is not strongly specialized in any given field, did not have a great impact factor in any given field either, except for clinical medicine. Its comparables had a greater impact in chemistry (IBMT) and in biomedical research (1,1).

Table 11 Average Relative Impact Factor* of NRC Biotechnology Institutes and Comparable Institutes by Field, 1992-1997

	BRI	GBF	IBT	IBD	IBMT	SINTEF	IBS	Nencki	ZMB	IMB	AIMS	Pacific	PBI	CSIRO	ECORC
Biology	1,4	1,0	0,6	n.s.		1,5	1,6	1,2	2,6	1,3	1,3	1,2	1,4	1,3	0,9
Biomedical Research	1,2	1,1	1,0	0,8	0,8	1,1	1,0	0,6	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,6	0,8	0,8	0,7
Chemistry	1,5	1,1	1,5	0,9	1,4	0,8	1,2		1,4	1,3	1,1		1,2	0,7	0,7
Clinical Medicine	1,3	1,1	1,7	1,2	1,0	0,9	1,3	1,0	0,9	0,6	0,6	0,8	n.s.	0,8	0,6
Earth and Space	1,4	1,9	1,0	n.s.			n.s.			n.s.	0,9	n.s.		1,0	1,0
Engineering & Techn	1,0	1,0	1,0	n.s.	1,1	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.		1,0	n.s.				
Mathematics															
Physics	1,2	0,4	n.s.	0,8	0,7	n.s.	1,0			0,9	0,6			0,9	n.s.
Unknown	3,1	1,3	0,6				n.s.					n.s.			
TOTAL	1,23	1,09	1,08	1,02	1,00	0,96	1,08	0,77	0,88	1,14	1,12	1,09	1,21	1,22	0,87

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

* Relative to G7

n.s. = non-significant (less than three papers published in journals with known impact factors).

8. Scientific Collaboration

Scientific collaboration is assessed in this study by analysing the co-authorship of papers. Scientific collaboration at the international level of NRC's biotechnology program rose from 63 to 87 papers annually between 1992 and 1997 (Figure 7). The share of papers written in international collaboration rose from 22% to 33%, which is similar to the trend observed for Canada as a whole. National collaborations were stable at around 42% of the total number of papers.

Figure 7 Collaborations of the NRC Biotechnology Program at the National and International Levels, 1992-1997

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

National Collaboration

About 88% of the NRC biotechnology program's national collaborations took place within the province where each institute is located (Table 12). Overall, the institutes collaborate most with Ontario (32% of the collaboration) followed closely by Quebec (28%). Nova Scotia and Saskatchewan each have about 10% of the collaboration while Manitoba has 7%, which put it on a par with Alberta (6%). The fact that Manitoba has so little collaboration is probably due at least partly to the youth of IBD which was created in the early 1990s.

About two-thirds of the NRC biotechnology program's collaborations were undertaken in the cities where the five institutes are located. Montreal has the greatest number of collaborations (189 collaborations including 152 with BRI). Ottawa follows closely (164 collaborations, of which 86 were with IBS) while Halifax (82 collaborations including 72 with IMB), Saskatoon (81 collaborations including 71 with PBI), and Winnipeg (59 collaborations including 38 with IBD) follow at a distance. Each institute tended to have about 45% of its collaborations with researchers in the city where it is located.

Table 12 Provincial Collaborations of NRC Biotechnology Institutes, 1992-1997

	BRI	IBD	IBS	IMB	PBI	TOTAL	NRC* (N)	FED** (N)
British-Columbia	1	1	12	3	10	27	182	851
Alberta	14	4	18	8	12	56	131	616
Saskatchewan	4	1	3	2	73	83	16	305
Manitoba	0	38	14	0	11	63	9	394
Ontario	65	34	128	28	22	277	779	4 164
Quebec	187	1	44	11	3	246	280	953
New-Brunswick	1	2	0	4	0	7	21	189
Nova-Scotia	1	2	7	83	2	95	29	323
Prince-Edward-Island	0	0	0	2	0	2	2	40
Newfoundland	1	1	1	6	0	9	26	124
Territories	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	25
TOTAL	274	84	227	147	133	865	1 476	7 984
N (736)	253	77	205	125	113	773	1 309	7 075

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

* Excluding the 5 NRC biotechnology centres

** Excluding NRC

The largest proportion of national collaborations of the NRC biotechnology program was with universities (61% of the collaborations), followed by federal laboratories and departments (21%, see Figure 9). This pattern is similar to that observed for the Canadian federal government in general but differs from that of the NRC as a whole (excluding the biotechnology program). The rest of the NRC collaborated more with universities (78%) and less with the federal government (8,5%).

Figure 8 Distribution of National Collaboration of NRC Biotechnology Program, 1992-1997

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

The NRC biotechnology program collaborated more than the rest of NRC with the hospital sector (7,5% vs. 0,6%) but it collaborated less with industry (5,3% vs. 7,9%).

The universities that collaborated the more closely with the NRC biotechnology institutes are, not surprisingly, closely located to the institutes (McGill, Saskatoon, Ottawa, Dalhousie, Manitoba).

BRI published a higher proportion of papers with the hospital sector (10,9%) than what was observed for the whole NRC biotechnology program. This is also the case for IBD (16,1%) and this institute also differs from others since it had no collaboration with industry in papers published between 1992 and 1997 (Table 13). IMB and PBI did not publish jointly to any large extent with the hospital sector (respectively 0,7% and 0,8 % of their collaborations), which could be expected given the nature of their mission. IMB collaborated more than other institutes with the federal government (32,5%) and with industry (9,3%).

Table 13 Number of national collaboration by sector, 1992-1997

	BRI	IBD	IBS	IMB	PBI	TOTAL	NRC* (N)	Fed** (N)
University	191	54	139	78	91	553	1 128	5 999
Federal Gvt	37	11	65	49	25	187	123	1 835
Hospital	33	14	19	1	1	68	9	184
Industry	19		8	14	7	48	114	618
Provincial Gvt	1	3			2	6	7	541
Other & Unknown	22	5	7	9	7	50	67	649
TOTAL	303	87	238	151	133	912	1 448	9 826
N (706)	253	77	202	128	113	773	1 309	8 196

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

* Excluding the 5 NRC biotechnology centres

** Excluding NRC

International Collaborations

Scientists from the NRC biotechnology program wrote a growing number of papers in collaboration with foreign researchers. The number of international collaborations and the growth rate of the collaborations are highly similar to that of comparable research institutes (Figure 9). NRC biotechnology institutes and comparable institutes increased their level of international collaboration by one third on average from 1992 to 1997.

BRI had the largest absolute number of international collaborations (152 which accounts for 28% of its papers) followed by IBS (142, that is, 31% of its papers). However, IBD had the largest percentage of papers written in international collaboration (41%).

The largest number of collaborations was with the United States (42% of the total). Collaboration was also sizeable with France, Germany, the United Kingdom and Japan. Together, the five countries accounted for 70% of the international collaboration of the NRC biotechnology programme.

Harvard University was the largest collaborator followed by the University of Washington and the Institut Pasteur.

Figure 9 Average Number of International Collaborations for NRC Biotechnology Institutes and for Comparable Institutes, 1992-1997

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

9. Conclusion

This study corroborates the results of previous studies on the scientific production of federal institutions⁵, namely:

- they produce a large number of papers;
- they produce a substantial share of the Canadian papers in their field of specialization;
- their papers have a high impact factor;
- they are linked with universities;
- they take part in international scientific networks.

In terms of absolute numbers, BRI published the most followed by IBS, while IMB, PBI and IBD follow at a distance. These five institutes produced more papers than NRC as a whole relative to budget allowances. For example, IBS produces 3,6 times as many papers as could be expected from the ratio of budget allocated to it (Table 14). IMB is also highly productive, with 2,4 times the percentage of NRC papers relative to the percentage of the budget. These are followed by BRI (2,1), IBD (1,8) and PBI (1,6).

Table 14 Production ratios for NRC biotechnology institutes, 1992-1997

	BRI	IBD	IBS	IMB	PBI	TOTAL
% of NRC papers*	10,8%	3,4%	9,1%	4,7%	4,5%	32,6%
% of NRC budget**	5,1%	1,9%	2,5%	2,0%	2,8%	14,3%
Ratio papers/budget	2,1	1,8	3,6	2,4	1,6	2,3
Average Relative Impact Factor***	1,2	1,0	1,1	1,1	1,2	1,1

Source: Observatoire des sciences et des technologies

* 1992-1997 period

** Based on financial year 1995-1996

*** Relative to G7 countries during 1992-1997 period

The scientific output of NRC biotechnology institutes, as measured by bibliometric methods, reveals work with a relatively high impact factor, that is, above the average paper of the G7 countries. The impact factor was also greater than that of average Canadian scientific papers, those produced by the Canadian federal government and was similar to those published by the rest of NRC (which had a 17% greater impact than the average G7 countries paper). The impact factor was also greater than that of comparable research institutes.

⁵ In particular, see the following OST studies: OST (2000) *The Canadian Government's Scientific Output: A Bibliometric Profile*; OST (2000) *Profil de la production scientifique d'Environnement Canada*, rapport présenté à Environnement Canada; OST (1999) *Scientific Production by Fisheries and Oceans Canada*, report presented to Fisheries and Oceans Canada. PDF version of the documents can be found at <http://www.ost.qc.ca/OSTE/HTML/Publications/Publications.htm>

Here is a summary of the performance of each institute in terms of the quality of its papers:

- BRI was the institute that published the paper with the greatest impact factor relative to papers written in G7 countries. It also has the greatest absolute number of papers as well as the greatest number of national and international collaborations. This suggests that BRI has both a local impact and an international recognition in its field of specialization, that is, biomedical research. Its impact factor is also higher than that of its comparables.
- PBI had the second largest average relative impact factor. Hence, although producing slightly less given the ratio of papers to financial resources than other institutes of the biotechnology program, it produced papers that had considerable impact. In particular, the papers written in the botany specialty, that is, the specialty of the institute, had an impact that is 40% greater than papers written in this specialty by the G7 countries. Its impact factor was about the same as that of its comparables.
- IMB had the third greatest average relative impact factor. Combined with the second highest ratio of papers to financial resources of the program, this institute also had a considerable impact in the specialties where it published most: analytical chemistry; botany, marine biology and hydrobiology. Its impact factor was similar to that of its comparables.
- IBS comes fourth only in terms of the quality of its papers (which was still 8% greater than the average G7 paper). However, papers by IBS in its speciality (biochemistry and molecular biology) had an impact that is about 15% lower than the average G7 paper, but this impact was higher than that of its comparables.
- IBD had the lowest quality papers of the program, although it is on a par with the average impact of a G7 country paper. This was coupled with a relatively low production ratio compared to other NRC biotechnology institutes. This might have been due to the fact that IBD did not have a strong specialization and also because this institute was and is the youngest of the five. Its impact was about the same as its comparables.

Hence, the biotechnology program as a whole produces papers of a similar quality to the rest of NRC and produced more than NRC as a whole relative to budget allocations. Globally, the five institutes showed a good performance relative to their comparables and relative to G7.

ANNEX I

Definitions

Index of Specialization

The index of specialization is calculated as follows:

$$\frac{\text{share (\%)} \text{ of papers of institution X in field Z}}{\text{share (\%)} \text{ of papers of all institutions in field Z}}$$

This index shows how specialized (i.e., active) an institution is in a particular field in comparison with other institutions. For example:

- Institution A has 200 biomedical research papers out of a total of 1 000 papers in all fields (meaning that 20% of its papers are in this field).
- All institutions considered have 3 000 biomedical research papers out of a total of 10 000 papers (30% of papers).

The index of specialization of institution A is therefore 0,66 (20% divided by 30%). which shows that this institution is not specialized in this field. In other words, it is less active in this field than the average institution. If the index is greater than 1, the institution is more active in a given field than the average institution in the same field.

Impact Factor

A journal's impact factor for a given year – 1996, for example – is calculated as follows:

$$\frac{\text{Number of citations received in 1996 for papers that appeared in the journal in 1994 and 1995}}{\text{Number of papers that appeared in the journal in 1994 and 1995}}$$

To calculate the average impact factor, each paper is assigned the impact factor of the journal in which it was published. Institutions whose researchers publish in journals with a high impact factor in a particular field will have a high impact factor in that field.

The average relative impact factor (ARIF) calculates the impact factor for every paper relative to the average impact in relevant sub-fields for a given unit of comparison (G7 in this report). An average factor is then calculated for every field and for every institute. A factor above 1 reveals that papers have a greater impact on average than G7 papers.